

A STUDY OF JOB SATISFACTION OF SCHOOL TEACHERS OF SIKKIM IN TERMS OF SELECT DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES

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ABSTRACT

Teachers are a fundamental resource in any learning set-up and their roles are not confined to only content delivery. However, the world of academia is rapidly witnessing changes on account of various reasons like health emergencies, formation of new policies, stress on quality learning, to name a few. Consequently, the roles and responsibilities of teachers are undergoing transformation. But teachers throughout the history and until present times have remained as a bridge between students and learning, as a facilitator of teaching learning and hence simplify the whole process of holistic development. For teachers to enact such multiple roles, it is essential for them to be physically and mentally sound and derive some satisfaction out of their job. Thus, with this understanding, the present study intended to investigate the job satisfaction of 300 secondary school teachers teaching in government schools of Sikkim concerning certain demographic variables. The study was conducted by administering a standardized tool of Job Satisfaction developed by Meera Dixit. The data was analyzed in SPSS by computing both descriptive and inferential statistics. The study revealed a significant difference in the job satisfaction of male and female teachers, likewise, a significant difference was found in terms of regular and ad-hoc teachers and teachers having different teaching experience also differed in their job satisfaction. The findings from the study can be beneficial in understanding the status of job satisfaction of government school teachers in Sikkim as such studies are scanty in number and also for devising some alternatives for refining the position of government school teachers.

Keywords : job satisfaction, government, gender, appointment, experience

Introduction

Job satisfaction, a concept more popular in the context of organisational behaviour is also relevant in case of teachers. It is the function of both intrinsic and extrinsic factors ranging from the teachers' attitude towards the intrinsic aspect of the job to certain external factors like pay, promotion, inter-personal relationship, working conditions, etc. The concept of job satisfaction is relatively old in origin. However, its meaning is still ambiguous on account of many models, theories and determinants that are often used by researchers to define it. Earlier attempts at defining job satisfaction are mainly focused on understanding its determinants or what

researchers call the motivators (Dinham & Scott, 1997) as cited in (Gkolia et al., 2014). For instance, Maslow's Theory of Hierarchy of Needs focuses on fulfilling human needs that are arranged in a hierarchy '(Gkolia et al., 2014). Fulfilment of lower order needs motivates a person to move up the ladder and direct the behaviour towards fulfilling the higher order needs. Gratification of needs culminates into job satisfaction. Similarly, another theory that clears our understanding of job satisfaction is the Two Factor Theory of Herzberg. Herzberg maintains that fulfilment of motivator needs leads to job satisfaction. On the contrary, non-fulfilment of hygiene needs leads to dissatisfaction '(Gkolia et al., 2014).

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Similarly, Vroom's Expectancy theory is also based on job motivators. For instance, if an individual expects that effective performance will be rewarded, the performance will be better (Mwamwenda, 1995).

Clearly then, there are various ways of defining job satisfaction based on many theoretical explanations and propositions. However, all attempts at defining it center around how well an individual's needs are fulfilled in the context of where the job is performed. Maslow's theory guides us towards the understanding that both intrinsic factors like self-esteem, self-actualization and extrinsic factors like inter-personal relationships, working conditions are crucial in deriving job satisfaction.

Researchers have also attempted to understand teachers' job satisfaction. In the context of teaching, it is understood as a sense of contentment that teachers derive out of their job on account of fulfillment of certain intrinsic and extrinsic aspects associated with teaching. According to Evans (1997) as cited in '(Tran, 2015) teachers' job satisfaction results from the extent to which teachers' needs like, fulfillment of teaching goals and recognition for accomplishments are met. Satisfied teachers help in realizing institutional goals to a considerable extent. It is therefore essential to make continuous efforts in understanding teachers' job satisfaction.

Related Literature

Job satisfaction of teachers has been explored with regard to many demographic variables. However, most of the researchers have concentrated on studying the gender differences and comparing the job satisfaction of government and private school teachers and reported mixed findings. Understanding the difference in teachers' job satisfaction as per their appointment is still under-explored as evident in the following paragraphs.

Gender and Job Satisfaction

Several studies focusing on gender differences in the job satisfaction of teachers have been conducted in the past. However, the conclusions from these studies are inconsistent as evident in the ongoing discussion. For instance, a study conducted by 'Tran (2015) found a significant gender difference and male teachers reported

higher job satisfaction than their female counterparts. Whereas few studies reported female teachers having better job satisfaction than males (Mocheche et al., 2017). On the contrary, some studies did not report any significant difference in the job satisfaction of male and female teachers, findings suggested no association between gender and job satisfaction (Menon & Athanasoula-Reppa, 2011). Similarly, few studies reported no significant difference between male and female teachers' job satisfaction (Bhuyan, 2016; Bhat, 2018). Likewise the study of Mabekoje (2009) reported no significant difference in teachers' job satisfaction based on gender.

Experience and Job Satisfaction

Teachers' job satisfaction has been explored in terms of teaching experience and the studies have reported diverse conclusions. For instance, one study reported teachers fresh in their teaching career experienced relatively higher job satisfaction (Khillah, 1986) as cited in '(Schroder, 2008). Likewise, Ma and MacMillan (1999) in '(Schroder, 2008) reported teachers at the verge of retirement experienced less job satisfaction. Some studies reported a considerable difference in the job satisfaction highly experienced teachers and less experienced teachers, teachers with higher teaching experience reportedly exhibited greater job satisfaction than less experienced teachers (Menon & Athanasoula-Reppa, 2011).

Nature of Appointment and Job Satisfaction

Very few attempts in the past have been made to explore the job satisfaction of teachers based on the appointment. In this regard, one study reported a significant difference in the job satisfaction of regular and contract teachers (Bhuyan, 2016).

Rationale of the Study

In Sikkim people are still dependent on securing government employment and teaching is still the favoured job for many. However, the efforts at studying the teachers' problems and issues are relatively inadequate. Therefore, the present study is highly significant given the understanding that studies conducted in terms of teachers' job satisfaction in Sikkim is at its nascent stage. Based on the findings certain

intervention strategies may be planned to address teachers' difficulties and problems. Additionally, the problem of ad-hoc teachers in Sikkim is very grave and majority of teachers in Sikkim from school to college level are appointed on ad-hoc basis. Thus, the findings from the study can guide the policy makers in devising certain policies in tackling the issues of ad-hoc teachers. Finally, the results of the study can guide the school authorities in framing some teacher-friendly policies and upgrade the facilities in school that can enhance their job satisfaction.

Statement of the Problem

The problem is stated as “A study of Job Satisfaction of School Teachers of Sikkim in Terms of Select Demographic Variables”.

Objectives of the Study

1. To explore the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers of Sikkim based on gender.
2. To determine the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers based on teaching experience.
3. To find out the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers on the basis of appointment.

Null Hypotheses

H₀₁ There is no significant gender difference in the job satisfaction of teachers.

H₀₂ There is no significant difference in the job satisfaction of teachers as per the nature of appointment.
H₀₃ There is no significant difference in the job satisfaction of teachers having different teaching experience.

Research Design

The study adopted descriptive research method to fulfill the objectives of the study. Survey was conducted to explore the job satisfaction of teachers.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample consisted of 300 teachers selected through Simple Random Sampling technique.

Tools Used

Job Satisfaction Scale constructed and standardized by Meera Dixit (2013) is used in the present study.

Results and Analysis

Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analysis and hypotheses testing. The results are presented in the succeeding paragraphs.

Null Hypothesis 1

There is no significant gender difference in the job satisfaction of teachers.

To test the above hypothesis *t* test was calculated as shown in Table 1:

Table 1

Mean Comparison of Secondary School Teachers Based on Gender

Variable	Gender	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>t</i> (298)	<i>p</i>
Job Satisfaction	Male	122	201.21	17.48	2.86	0.00
	Female	178	195.45	16.89		

Table 1 shows the results of *t* test that was performed to test null hypothesis 1. The result suggests a significant difference in the job satisfaction of male and female teachers with *t* (298)=2.86, *p*<0.05). Additionally, the result suggests male teachers with (*M*=201.21, *SD*=17.48) having higher job satisfaction than females with (*M*=195.45, *SD*=16.89). Thus, the results indicate that male teachers are comparatively more satisfied with

their job than females. Therefore, H₀₁ was rejected.

Null Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the job satisfaction of teachers as per the nature of appointment.

The investigators performed *t* test to test the above null hypothesis as shown in Table 2.

Table 2*Mean Comparison of Secondary School Teachers Based on Appointment*

Variable	Appointment	<i>n</i>	Mean	SD	<i>t</i> (298)	<i>p</i>
Job	Regular	144	199.93	17.68		
Satisfaction	Ad-hoc	156	195.82	16.83	2.06	0.04

Table 2 shows the results of independent samples *t* test that was performed to test null hypothesis 2. As evident from the table, there were significant difference in the job satisfaction of regular and ad-hoc teachers with $t(298)=2.06, p<0.05$. Regular teachers with ($M=199.93, SD=17.68$) were relatively ahead than ad-hoc teachers with ($M=195.82, SD=16.83$). Based on the result of *t* test,

the investigators rejected H_{02} . Thus, it was concluded that there is a significant difference in the job satisfaction of teachers according to their nature of appointment.

Null Hypothesis 3

H_{03} There is no significant difference in the job satisfaction of teachers having different teaching experience.

Table 3*Mean, Standard Deviation, and One-Way Analysis of Variance in Job Satisfaction Across Teaching Experience Groups*

Variable	<10 Years		10-20 Years		>20 Years		<i>F</i> (2, 334)	Post-hoc
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>		
	Job Satisfaction	195.52	16.45	198.13	16.59	205.63		

Table 3 shows the results of one-way ANOVA that was computed to test the null hypothesis. Based on the results, it is clear that there existed a significant difference in the job satisfaction of teachers having different years of teaching experience with $F(2, 297) = 7.24, p < 0.05$. Therefore, the H_{03} was rejected and it was concluded that a significant difference exists in the job satisfaction of teachers with varying service lengths. Further, post-hoc assessment showed the job satisfaction of teachers above twenty years to be highest in comparison to teachers between ten to twenty years and teachers having less than ten years of service. Teachers with less than ten years of service had the least job satisfaction.

Findings and Discussion

In terms of the first objective of the study, the investigators found a significant difference in the job satisfaction of male and female teachers. Female teachers

reported low job satisfaction. H_{01} was not confirmed. However, the conclusion validated the finding of Tran (2015). On the contrary, it opposed the finding of (Mocheche et al., 2017).

As regards the second objective, the study found a significant difference in the job satisfaction of regular and ad-hoc teachers. Regular teachers had better job satisfaction. Hence, H_{02} was rejected. Nevertheless, the finding meets the investigators' expectations and aligns with the study of Bhuyan (2016). Ad-hoc teachers' poor job satisfaction is well-established in Sikkim and reasons like job insecurity, poor salary, lack of opportunities for promotion etc. explain their plight.

Regarding the third objective, the study reported a substantial difference in the job satisfaction of teachers having varying length of teaching experience. Teachers with maximum duration of service were the most

satisfied, whereas teachers with minimum service length were least satisfied. H_{03} was not supported. The result aligns with the study of Menon and Athanasoula-Reppa (2011). Whereas, it contrasted the studies of Khillah (1986) as cited in 'Schroder (2008). Likewise, it also opposed the study of Ma and MacMillan (1999) in '(Schroder, 2008). Better experience of senior teachers in handling students on account of their prolonged service tenure, job security, better financial rewards, recognition etc. could perhaps explain the finding.

Conclusion

In any educational set-up teachers are a key resource. The roles they enact and the duties they perform decide to a great extent the institutional growth and progress, and students' achievement. The findings hinted at the existence of poor job satisfaction of female, ad-hoc, and less experienced teachers. This certainly is a cause of concern, since the bulk of teaching fraternity comprise of females, ad-hoc and freshly appointed teachers. Thus, the findings could perhaps guide the stakeholders to understand the various reasons for low job satisfaction of teachers and plan strategies to address these issues. Moreover, future researchers could make systematic inquiry into understanding the antecedents of poor job satisfaction of certain categories of teachers and propose a better explanation for low job satisfaction.

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